

CHAKRAMARDA –A REVIEW OF LOCALLY GROWN LEAFY VEGETABLE

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INTRODUCTION

Knowledge of this drugs are known from Vedas, Samhitas, Nighantus and Sangraha Grathans. Botanical source of plant is Cassia Tora Linn of Fabaceae family. In India and other countries Chakramarda is known for its medicinal uses. During rainy seen Chakramarda can be get easily available. It is seen growing in roadsides wastelands. It is Katu Rasatmaka along with Katu Vipaka and Ushna Virya having Guna like Laghu, Ruksha and is Kaphavatshamka. Chakramarda has been mentioned to treat various diseases like Dadru, Krimi, Kushta, etc. Chakramarda leaves decoction is used in piles. Leaf has hepatoprotective and anti-inflammatory property. It is poor man's food because of proteins, small amount of fat, minerals and fibres. Chakramarda seeds in chineses medicine is used as aperients, antiasthma, diuretic agent and improves visual activity. It is a weed found throughout in India, ascending up to an altitude of 1550m in Himalaya, distributed in Himachal

Pradesha, Bihar, Odisha, Bengal, Punjab, Rajasthan, on wasteland and along road side of Maharashtra and Karnataka. It is an annual herb, 30-90cm high. Leaves green in colour. Leaflets are in 3 pairs, distinctly petioled, opposite, conical at on end, ovate, oblong and base oblique. Flowers are pale yellow.

Taxonomical classification

Kingdom: plantae; sub division: tracheobionta; division: spermatophyta; class: mangnoliopsida; sub class: Rosidae; order: fabales; family: Fabaceae/ leguminosae; genus: cassia Mill.-senna; species: cassia tora.

MATERIALS AMD METHODS

To learn and understand about the drug available in Ayurvedic literature collected from sources like Samhitas, books related to medicinal plants, Nighantus, research articles, journals and use of internet for more information regarding this drug.

Synonyms

1. Meshlochan: leaves like that of Mesha eyes.
2. Uranakhya: seeds like Sambars eye.
3. Dadru Beeja: hard nature of seed.
4. Edgaj: ringworm.
5. Dadrughna: treats Dadru.
6. Chakri: kills ringworm.
7. Kharjughna: cures Kandu.
8. Kushtaghna: cures Kushta.
9. Pamagati: cures Pama.
10. Chakramarda: treat ringworm infestation.
11. Prapunnad: used by humans for internal purpose.

Pharmacological properties

1. Dhanawantari Nighantu: Katu Rasa, Ushna Virya, Vatakaphaghna, cures Kandu and Dadru.
2. Madanpal Nighnatu: Vatapittaghna.
3. Kaidev Nighnatu: Madhura and Lavana rasa and Sheeta Virya, Laghu, Guru, Ruksha Guna, Vatakaphaghna, cures Kandu, Gulma, Kasa.
4. Bhavprakash Nighantu: Katu Rasa, Ushna Virya.
5. Nighantu Ratnakar: Madhur Rasa, Laghu, Ruksha Guna, Pittavataghna.
6. Shaligram Nighantu: Katu Rasa, Sheeta Guna, Vatapittaghna, cures Kushta, Kandu, Krumighna.
7. Priya Nighantu: cures Kandum Dadru.
8. Nighantu Adarsh: Madhura and Katu Rasa, Katu Vipaka, Ushna Virya, Vatakaphaghna.

Classification

Samhita Kala: in Charaka Samhita: Shakavarga; in Sushrut Samhita, Urdwbhagahara Gana.

Nighantu Kala: Dhanawantari Nighantu, Shodhal Nighantu- Karaviryadi Varga; Kaidev Nighantu: Aushadi Varga; Bhavprakash Nighantu-Haritakyadi Varga; Raj Nighantu-Shatahvadi Varga; Shaligram Nighantu: Ashtavarga.

In Charak Samhita, it is referred to as Edagaja and is indicated for skin diseases, piles, ringworm, worms, Dadru, and Shvitra, primarily for external application. It is also used in conditions like mandala Kushta, Krimi, and Kandu, and administered in forms such as Kanaka Kshiri Taila. In Sushrut Samhita, under the synonym Prapunnad, it is indicated for Shvitra and Mahakushta, used as Lepa (external paste) and Kwatha (decoction). Chakramarda is specifically recommended for Dadru in Lepa form. In Bhavaprakasha, it is described for Kandu and Mandala Kushta, used in preparations like Madhyamanjishtadi Kwatha, Mahamarichyadi Taila, Saindhavadi Taila, and Durvadi Yoga. It is also indicated for Pama, Kandu, Dadru, Kushta, and Shitapitta, with dosage forms including Churna and medicated oils. Yoga Ratnakar mentions its use in Kushta, severe itching, Pama, Charmadala, Vicharchika, and Kushta complex, administered as Lepa, Panchanimba Churna, Brihatsindura Taila, and Maheshwar Ghrita.

Ethno-medically, various parts of Chakramarda are used for treating eczema (root applied locally), warts (leaf paste applied for seven days), ringworm (leaf juice mixed with lemon applied locally), vaginal discharge (root ground with rice water), migraine (seed paste with kanji applied locally), Vasa Meha (root decoction), and Shitapitta (seed powder with ghee). Traditionally, rural and tribal communities of the Satpura region of Madhya Pradesh use the plant for multiple ailments. It is valued for its effect on liver and large intestine channels, reducing heat and improving vision. Due to its fungicidal properties, it is also used as a natural pesticide in organic farming. Seed powder is utilized in the pet food industry and in mining and other industrial applications when mixed with guar gum.

Classically, Chakramarda is used in Siddham Kushta (root with kanji for local application), Shiro Roga (seeds with Amla Dravya applied locally), and Gandamala, where root paste is cooked with Bhringarajaswarasa and Sarshapa Taila to prepare medicated oil. It is also included in formulations like Chakramarda Taila.

Chemically, the leaves contain anthraquinone glycosides, flavonoids, sennosides, and kaempferol-3-diglucoside. The seeds contain anthraquinone, naphthopyrone, naphthopyrone glycosides, cassiaside, and chrysophanic acid-9-anthone. The seed oil contains oleic, linoleic, palmitic, stearic, and lignoceric acids. Other plant parts such as pods contain sennosides; flowers contain kaempferol and leucopelargonidine; roots contain leucopelargonidine and beta-sitosterol; and the stem contains fatty acids including arachidic, isostearic, palmitic, marginic, and behenic acids. Panwar gum obtained from the seeds consists of neutral heteropolysaccharides of galactose and mannose.

Pharmacological properties

Chakramarda (*Cassia tora* Linn.) exhibits multiple pharmacological properties. The methanolic extract of its seeds shows strong antioxidant activity. Leaf extracts demonstrate antifertility effects, possibly linked to estrogenic action. The plant also possesses antigenotoxic properties, as confirmed by laboratory assays such as the Ames test and comet assay. It shows significant antifungal activity against organisms like *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus niger*, mainly due to anthraquinones such as chrysophanol and related compounds. Anti-inflammatory activity has been observed in experimental models, particularly against induced edema. The plant also has purgative action, likely due to anthraquinone derivatives like emodin. Additionally, chloroform, methanol, and aqueous extracts exhibit antimicrobial activity against various bacteria and fungi responsible for skin and gastrointestinal infections.

Referred management

Case study evaluates the efficacy of Chakramard Beeja Churna (*Cassia tora*) in the management of Dadru (tinea/ringworm), a common fungal skin infection characterized by itching, redness, papules, and dryness, mainly due to Kapha-Pitta predominance. The study was conducted on 30 patients, with local application of Chakramarda Beeja Churna mixed with lukewarm water for 30 minutes daily over one month, followed by weekly assessment. Results showed significant improvement in symptoms such as Kandu (itching), raga (redness), Pidika (lesions), and Twak Rukshata (dryness), with visible reduction in lesions. Thus, Chakramarda, having antifungal and Kushthaghna properties, was found to be effective in the management of Dadru Kushtha.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Chakramarda has been extensively mentioned in classical Ayurvedic literature and traditional medical systems as an important medicinal herb. Various ancient texts describe multiple synonyms (Paryaya) assigned to this plant, reflecting its morphological features, habitat, and therapeutic actions. Around twenty-five traditional names are recorded across Ayurvedic scriptures, highlighting its long-standing medicinal significance.

Different Ayurvedic scholars have described its pharmacological attributes differently. Most Acharyas have classified its dominant taste (Rasa) as Katu (pungent), while some texts describe it as Madhura (sweet) or a combination of Madhura and Katu. Only a few classical sources elaborate on its Vipaka (post-digestive effect), describing it as Katu. These variations indicate interpretative differences among classical authors but collectively confirm its therapeutic relevance, particularly in skin disorders and metabolic conditions.

CONCLUSION

Chakramarda is a traditionally valued medicinal plant with wide therapeutic applications, especially in skin diseases, fungal infections, and disorders related to vata imbalance. Modern studies support its traditional claims by identifying several bioactive constituents responsible for antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antifungal, and purgative activities. Although existing research validates many of its classical uses, further well-designed clinical studies are necessary to establish its safety, efficacy, and dosage standards. With continued scientific evaluation, Chakramarda holds significant potential for broader medicinal application.

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